

Design of intellectual tracking system controller for Infusion Pump in medical applications

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Abstract

In this paper, we model and investigate controllers for infusion pump system to actuate air control flow with improved performance. The actuator is realized with permanent magnet brushless DC motor controlled by self tune PID controller replaced self tune fuzzy-PID controller. Using nonlinear model of the infusion pump system includes the motor driver, fuzzy-PID controller and gear head as load connected to analysis experimental results. The proposed control topology will improve transient response such as rise time and steady state error of the infusion pump system. Actuation system needs efficient actuator with controller for tracking desired response with self tuning depends on linear and nonlinear condition. The complete electro mechanical actuator for fin control is modeled in MATLAB/SIMULINK environment. The simulation results show that the better transient response and less torque ripples in proposed system and a comparison study is performed for fuzzy-PID and conventional PID controller.

Keywords: Fuzzy PID controller, Infusion Pump, BLDC motor, self tune

I. Introduction

The use of electro-mechanical actuation system is increase day by day in many tracking applications to improve actuation system performance [1]. Electro-mechanical actuation system is being used in the actuation system of infusion pump and infusion pumps [2-4]. The actuator needs to maintain constant torque performance for various dynamic loads. Brushless DC motor is intensively used in many applications like aerospace defence and industrial automation. Electro

mechanical actuator needs better torque-speed characteristics for which BLDC motor is an ideal choice as actuator system [5-7]. A drive system for BLDC motor is developed on current control techniques using PWM signals. Among the controller, conventional PID is most popular controller in practice has poor dynamic behavior for nonlinear loads in real time applications [8-10].

Figure.1 Overview of Infusion Pump

A control algorithm integrating a fuzzy-PID controller and a Brushless DC drive as shown in figure.1. The control algorithm performs fast operation with fuzzy-PID controller for nonlinear systems and overcome its oscillatory response by switching gains of the fuzzy-PID controller [21, 22]. The proposed controller has shorter in rise time, less overshoot and oscillation than PID control, which is an ideal requirement for underwater infusion pumps. To verify the proposed system the complete setup was simulated in MATLAB-SIMULINK environment.

II. Modeling of Intelligent Controller

Modeling and tuning of controller is a difficult task in BLDC motor drive system. The design of BLDC motor drive controller requires three feedback closed loops in considering current speed and position. The first closed loop is a current controller performs in limiting the maximum current to protect the motor and second closed loop is speed controller to maintain the fin at desired speed

limit. The outer (third) closed loop is a position controller to maintain the fin at set desired position in infusion pumps. The PID controllers are used for feedback system due to its simplicity and easy to operate conventionally, shows poor performance during the change in load and change of commands. Tuning the control gain is tedious and time consuming. To overcome the limitations fuzzy based PID controllers is proposed. Fuzzy PID does not require complex mathematical modeling and they are more suitable in nonlinear environment. It extends its advantage with minimized error and faster response compare than conventional one

Figure.2 Conventional PID controller

The basic model of conventional PID controller as shown in figure.2 is used in position, speed and current controllers but their gain values K_p , K_i and K_d are differed as per the position and current magnitude working ranges. From the PID control law, the mathematical formulation of discrete controller is formed as per equation 1. The control gain values are determined using Ziegler-Nichols method of tuning.

$$C(z) = K_p + K_i T \frac{z}{z-1} + \frac{K_d}{T} \frac{z-1}{z} \quad (3)$$

- K_p - Proportional gain
- K_i - Integral gain
- K_d - Derivative gain
- T - Sampling time in sec

Using the change of measurement instead of change of error is to prevent the step change in reference signal from directly triggering the derivative action. The range of membership is function

used as unity ± 1 , and hence it is required to scale the control signals before and after fuzzy inference [17-21].

Figure.3 Combination of Fuzzy PID controller

Reference current magnitude I_{dc}^* is the output of outer loop position controller and gate pulse duty cycle is the output of inner loop current controller and compared with actual measured and feed current controller. The scaling factors are derived from conventional PID controller gains as per equation (4)-(7). One feed forward path is provided to ensure the working of proportional action when the fuzzy PID controller is linear. Anti-windup feature is included to control the saturation level of output response signal, so as to improve the quick response of the fuzzy PID controller.

$$GE = \frac{1}{\max \text{ error}} \quad (4)$$

$$GCE = GE * \left(K_p - \sqrt{K_p^2 - 4K_i K_d} \right) \frac{K_i}{2} \quad (5)$$

$$GU = \frac{K_d}{GCE} \quad (6)$$

$$GCU = \frac{K_i}{GE} \quad (7)$$

- GE - Error normalization factor
- GCE - Change in measurement normalization factor
- GU - Response de-normalization factor
- GCU - Change in response de-normalization factor

Input and output variables are mapped via membership functions to work with fuzzy inference system. They are triangular and cross neighbor sets at membership value of 1 as shown in figure 11. Mamdani type inference is used for inference engine and center of gravity method is used for defuzzification. The linguistic variables are divided into seven groups and they are nl - negative large, nm - negative medium, ns - negative small, nz-negative zero, z- zero, pz- positive zero ps-positive small, pm - positive medium and pl - positive large [22].

Fig.4 Membership Functions of ‘e’ ‘ce’ ‘u’

TABLE I- Fuzzy rule-based matrix

e \	nl	nm	Ns	nz	z	pz	ps	pm	pl
nl	nl	nl	Nl	nl	nl	nl	nm	ns	z
nm	nl	nl	Nl	nl	nm	nm	ns	z	ps
ns	nl	nl	Nm	nm	ns	ns	z	ps	pm
nz	nl	nl	Nm	ns	z	ps	pm	ps	pm
z	nl	nm	Ns	ns	z	ps	ps	pm	pm
pz	nm	ns	Ns	ps	z	pm	pz	ps	pl
ps	nm	ns	Z	ps	ps	pm	pm	pl	pl
pm	ns	z	ps	ps	pm	pl	pl	pl	pl
pl	z	ps	pm	pm	pl	pl	pl	pl	pl

Inference engine work is based on rules as per table II, there are $9 \times 9 = 81$ rules are possible in the matrix. The top row and left column of the matrix indicate the fuzzy set of the variables ‘e’ and ‘ce’ respectively and the variable ‘u’ is shown in the body of the matrix. The surface view of the fuzzy PID controller is shown in figure 12, whereas the x-axis is error ‘e’, y-axis is change in measurement ‘ce’ and z-axis is output response ‘u’. The resulting plot shows smooth surface.

Figure.5 Surface viewer of fuzzy PID controller

Figure.6 Simulink Block diagram of infusion pump

III. Simulation and Results

Infusion pump fin position control drive is simulated in for commanded signal and several tests are performed to validate the controller design. The analysis for conventional PID and fuzzy PID controller response are presented in figure. 7 &8 to verify the dynamic behavior in terms speed, current and back-EMF of proposed controller. Simulation is carried up to 0.2 seconds and the initial position was changed for commanded value of 2100 counts.

doi:10.3906/elk-

Fig.7: Conventional PID controller for INFUSION PUMP

Fig.8: Fuzzy PID controller for INFUSION PUMP

For step change of speed analysis is carried are as shown in Fig.9 show the speed step up from 5000rpm into 10000rpm at 0.05 sec then step down to 10000rpm into 5000rpm at 0.1 sec. The results suggest in speed control fuzzy performance is better than conventional one including settling errors. In proposed system two gear heads are designed with gear ratio of 1:14 and 1:135. The incremental encoder will increment the pulse counts of 0.25 in each edge. So one revolution of motor will give us 100ppr that can be possible in 400 edges then (400*14*135) 100 pulse counts are possible for one revolution. The pulse counts required for 360° is 756000 pulse counts, for one degree fin movements 2100 pulse counts. The fin is required to move ±2° then in that case position analysis is carried for 4100 counts.

Figure.9 Speed control for INFUSION PUMP system

The maximum fin movement is either forward or reverse direction 2°. When the forward direction is from 0° to 2° so as position commands for 0 to 2100 counts as shown in figure 10, drive operates in the first quadrant of forward motoring (FM) because speed and torque is same positive sign. When infusion pump fin reaches 2°, torque at maximum and speed will starts reduces. This will increase the reaching time of reference position. The conventional PID required 0.35 sec of settling time (Ts) but fuzzy PID reached at 0.19 sec. A comparison is made with the dynamic behaviors and presented in table 3. The rising time (Tr), percentage of maximum overshoot (Mp) and ± percentage of steady state error, the performance of fuzzy PID is better than conventional one in all operating conditions of commanded signals.

Table.3: Result comparison of Conventional PID and Fuzzy PID

Controller	Conventional PID				Fuzzy PID			
Parameter	Tr (milli-sec)	Mp (%)	Ts (milli-sec)	± Error (%)	Tr (milli-sec)	Mp (%)	Ts (milli-sec)	± Error (%)
Set Position								

Step change motion 0 to 2100 counts	0.65	0	0.35	-6.66	0.54	1.11	0.19	+1.22
Step change motion 2100 to 4200 counts	0.1	22.22	0.2	+5.55	0.15	5.55	0.25	+1.66
Step change motion 4200 to 2100 counts	0.2	0	0.35	-5.55	0.15	1.11	0.25	-1.33
Step change motion 2100 to 0 counts	0.1	22.22	0.2	-3.33	0.15	5.55	0.25	-1.44

Further, algorithm achieved with less rise time makes key improvements in over all tracking system with less rise rime and settling time. The up-to-date investigation and experimental results tabulated is directed to implement fuzzy-PID controller for all tracking applications holds better tracking response

Conclusion

A fuzzy-PID tracking method is presented and compared conventional self tune-PID controller. Initially a experimental test is carried in MATLAB SIMULINK and comparison results describes the superior of proposed fuzzy control algorithm. A hardware prototype is developed using dSPACE and drive motor and acquires a real time performance in control desk. The test results confirm the proposed fuzzy-PID control algorithm stability and its effective tracking over conventional methods.

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